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PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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DAYANARA P. BESA, PhD

Faculty

Sultan Kudarat State University

dayanara.besa@umindanao.edu.ph

“HEY, JOHN”

How are you? I hope you're doing well. I just wanted you to know that you've been on my mind lately. You are the reason why I found the courage to write again. Thank you for your presence last December — you made me feel so special.

I miss your gestures, your attention, and the way you made me feel beautiful and valued. I still remember your smile, your face, your aura... even your beautiful teeth and how clean and put-together you always were. Most of all, I remember the way you looked at me — it was as if you saw right through me, and yet you made me feel safe.

Thank you for being brave enough to approach me and talk to me. I remember how much courage it must have taken — and yet, you did it anyway. You made the effort to speak with me every day, observing me, running just to join me walking, just to talk with me — and I noticed. I truly noticed. You have become the standard, John.

I hope you're doing okay. I sincerely wish you all the best in life — in your career, your family, and in finding your own happiness. I pray that the Lord blesses you abundantly and grants you everything your heart desires.

And maybe, just maybe, I hope He allows our paths to cross again — perhaps soon, or in a very special way.

Until then... see you when I see you, John.

Always,
Me